

A Basic Typology of Product Emotions

Pieter Desmet, Department of Industrial Design, Delft University of Technology - The Netherlands

Abstract

The fact that we are capable of distinguishing many distinct emotions is illustrated by the vast number of emotion-denoting words that exists in most human languages. In the English language, for example, researchers have reported lists of up to 400 words to cover the full range of human emotions. Given this abundance, most emotion researchers rely on typologies of emotions to structure their studies. Although this approach seems applicable to studies of design and emotion, the available typologies may be too general for design research. Therefore, this paper reports the development of a typology of product emotions, that is, emotions likely to be elicited (or often elicited) by consumer products. For this development, a multistage method was used. The starting point was an extensive set of 374 emotions that was reduced to a manageable set of 25 emotions in a series of successive steps. The application value of the set is discussed in relation to the often-applied basic emotion typologies. It was found that although most basic emotions are not regularly evoked by products, particular derivatives of most basic emotions can be found in the typology of product emotions. In addition, it was found that the typology includes some emotions that cannot be derived from the basic emotions. The implications of these findings for design and emotion research are discussed, and further research directions are indicated.

Keywords: typology, emotion, basic emotions, emotion types

Introduction

In 1995 British artist Damien Hirst won the prestigious Turner prize with his work 'mother and child divided,' a cross-cut of a pregnant cow moulded in perspex. Both the concept and the design of this work are simple and straightforward. What makes this and similar works especially interesting is that, in contrast to the concept's straightforwardness, the observers' emotional responses are complex and layered. Emotions may be stirred by the peaceful serenity of floating animals, the beauty and perfection of these creations of nature, the frightening and revolting look inside an animal, and also the guts it took for Hirst to create these works, the scandal that they are considered art, and so on. Naturally, in that sense, his work is not unique. In fact, much (if not most) art, from Duchamp's toilet to Jef Koons' 'art-porn,' elicits layered, or 'paradoxical' emotions, and Frijda and Schram (1995) stated that in art it is precisely these paradoxical emotions that we seek and enjoy. Evidently, a consumer product is not the same as a work of art. Products are produced and sold with a commercial intent, and bought and used because they are anticipated to serve a particular function in one's life. Nevertheless, similar to our response to art, consumer products can stir powerful and complex emotional responses. Our studies support the idea that even conventional

products, such as mobile telephones and fabric softeners, can evoke layered emotional profiles (see e.g. Desmet 2003). The last few years we have been exploring the possibilities to employ such emotion profiles as the starting-point for new 'emotionally innovative' designs (e.g. Desmet and Dijkhuis, 2003). In these case studies we found that by understanding and measuring different types of emotional responses, it was possible to design products that target specific types of emotions, not just a diffuse, generalized pleasant emotional state. However, these studies also indicated that some emotions are evoked more often than others. To be able to focus our efforts, our question therefore was: can products elicit any possible emotion, or are the responses limited to a particular 'subset' of emotions? Given the fact that most psychologists who study human emotions are generally more interested in (the process of) emotions 'as such' than in the antecedent or eliciting conditions, little is known about the place of product emotions in our emotional repertoire. Therefore, this paper reports a first sketch of an empirical based typology of emotional responses to products. In the typology the distinction is made between emotions evoked by the first encounter with the product (that is, by the product appearance), and those evoked by owning and using the product. This typology should interest researchers investigating emotional responses evoked by products and to other product-related domains of interest.

Emotion types

Traditional behavioural theories of emotion tended to conceptualize emotion as undifferentiated physiological arousal. More recently, two-dimensional models have been proposed that add a pleasantness dimension to the arousal dimension (e.g. Russell, 1980). The major claim of those following this approach is that emotions are best described and differentiated by the use of these underlying dimensions. This claim entails that emotions are interrelated, and thus that some emotions are more similar (e.g. anger versus irritation) than others (e.g. boredom versus inspiration). The major criticism of the dimensional approach is that, although it can categorize emotions, dimensions are not sufficient to differentiate between emotions. The unmistakably different emotions anger and fear, for example, do not differ in terms of pleasantness and arousal. In addition, starting in the 1960s, evidence has increasingly supported the conception that there are several distinct emotions (such as joy and anger), as manifest in different facial expressions observable across cultures (Ekman 1984) and in characteristic action tendencies such as approach, inaction, avoidance, and attack (see

Frijda, 1986). As a consequence, most modern theorists of emotion have adopted a categorical rather than a dimensional approach of emotion.

Shaver and his colleagues, who work with this approach, consider emotions to be fuzzy sets that are organised around abstract prototypes (Shaver *et al.* 1987). In their prototype approach, all the emotion lexicon, containing hundreds of terms, refer in one way or another to a mere handful of basic-level emotions. Our emotions are structured in a hierarchical organisation with three major levels of inclusiveness: the superordinate (unpleasant emotion), the basic (sadness), and the subordinate (grief). The middle level is called ‘basic’ because basic-level categories are learned first during language acquisition, and are accessed most quickly when a relevant stimulus is encountered. In other words, the basic level emotions represent the core of the repertoire of our emotions. Although several theorists have assembled sets of such ‘basic’ emotions, the most applied set, which is assembled by Ekman (1971), includes six emotions: surprise, joy, sadness, disgust, fear, and anger. Basic emotion theorists’ consider all other –secondary- emotions to be derived from these basic emotions. According to Shaver and his colleagues, each emotion term refers to a basic emotion, and to its intensity or specific eliciting context, or both. Thus, emotion terms specify either the intensity of the particular basic emotion in question (e.g. jubilation vs. satisfaction, rage vs. grouchiness, and terror vs. worry) or the antecedent context in which the emotion arises (disappointment vs. grief, pride vs. hope).

Although this approach provides us with a concise structure of emotion types, for two reasons the application possibilities for design research are limited. First, it is very difficult to derive some emotions that one would intuitively consider to be relevant for product experience from any of the basic emotions. For example, it seems farfetched to consider the emotions boredom and desire to be a specification of anger, fear, sadness, disgust, or joy. Second, the distinctions between the basic emotions seem to be too rudimentary to capture the variety of emotional responses to product design. Anger, for example, comes in many flavours (e.g. dissatisfaction; indignation; aversion), and the differences between these flavours may be not less important than their likeness. Also, the basic emotion set includes only one pleasant emotion, i.e. joy, and it would be over-simplified to consider all pleasant emotional responses to products to be mere joy-variations. Given these limitations, it was decided to develop a typology that does right to the variety in emotional responses evoked by product design and at the same time shares the conciseness of the basic emotion typologies.

Basic set of product emotions

Researchers in the domain of marketing who recognise the above described limitations of basic emotion typologies have developed alternative typologies tailored for advertising (e.g. Batra and Holbrook, 1990; Aaker, Stayman, and Vezina, 1988). Although interesting, these typologies are not applicable to the current domain because advertising may evoke other emotions than product design. In addition, not all terms that are included in these typologies refer to emotions in particular or affective states in general (such as ‘ugly’ and ‘incorporated’ in the Aaker typology). For the specific domain of product design it was therefore decided to develop a new typology. A multistage method was used that is similar to methods used in earlier studies in psychology (e.g. Davitz, 1969). Because this method was previously discussed in detail (see Desmet, 2002), in the current paper a summary is reported. The starting point was an extensive set of emotions that was reduced to a manageable set in a series of four successive steps. First, a set of emotions was assembled that is sufficiently extensive to represent a general overview of the full repertoire of human emotions. This set of 347 emotions was compiled by merging lists of emotions reported in the psychologist literature. The first study was designed to categorize these emotions and to omit those that are unclear or ambiguous. For the categorization, eight categories were created with the use of the dimensions pleasantness and arousal. Participants ($N = 20$) rated all emotions on these dimensions with a three-point scale: pleasant-neutral-unpleasant, and calm-moderate-excited respectively. In addition, participants marked emotion words with which they were not familiar. The resulting eight subsets of emotions served as the starting point for the second study.

The aim of the second study was to select those emotions that are most often elicited by products. In this study, participants ($N = 22$) used a rating procedure to indicate which emotions they often, and which they do not often experience in response to product appearance. They were instructed to do this for each of the eight emotion sets. On the basis of the sum scores, 69 emotions were selected that are evoked regularly by product design (the sum scores of these emotions were significantly higher than the average score). Examples of emotions that were not found to be evoked regularly by product design are rage, humiliated, and passionate, whereas emotions such as inspired, satisfied, and disappointed were reported to be experienced often in response to product design. Subsequently, in the third step, the set was further shortened by eliminating those emotions that are approximately similar to others in the set. Participants ($N = 40$) rated the similarity of the emotions in pairs. With the use of a

hierarchical cluster analysis, the set of 69 emotions was reduced to a set of 41 emotions. Examples of emotions that have been identified as duplicate emotions were irritated & annoyed, and cheerful & joyful.

In a final study, participants ($N = 23$) rated all 41 emotions on a five-point scale (from ‘very relevant to product experience’ to ‘not relevant to product experience’). As the aim of this study was to exclude those emotions that are least relevant, it was decided to exclude all emotions that have a mean score that is significantly lower than the overall means score. This resulted in the following set of 25 emotions (in alphabetical order):

admiration; alarmed; amazement; amusement; astonishment; avaricious; boredom; contempt; curiosity; desire; disappointment; disgust; dissatisfaction; eagerness; fascination; indignation; inspiration; irritation; joyful; pleasant surprise; satisfaction; softened; stimulation; unpleasant surprise; yearn.

These emotions are all regularly experienced in response to consumer products. The list includes both pleasant emotions (e.g. desire and admiration), unpleasant emotions (e.g. irritation and contempt), and emotions that are neutral (e.g. stimulated and amazement). The emotions in the set represent both the basic level (e.g. disgust and joyful), and the subordinate level in the hierarchical structure of emotions (e.g. dissatisfaction and irritation). The next section presents a typology that was created by bringing the emotions in the set to the same ‘basic’ level.

Typology of product emotions

At first sight, there seems to be little agreement between Ekman’s six basic emotions and the product relevant emotions. Only two can be found in both sets: joy and disgust. However, if we examine the emotions on the subordinate level, greater agreement can be observed. Then, in fact, derivatives of almost all basic emotions can be found in the set of product emotions. The first five columns of Table 1 show those product relevant emotions that are basic emotion derivatives. The emotions that are classified under a particular basic emotion can be considered subordinate level emotion terms. Amusement, for example, refers to the emotion joy with a particular antecedent condition. Similarly dissatisfaction and indignation both refer to the emotion anger with each a specified antecedent condition.

<i>Basic emotion derivates</i>					
<i>Surprise</i>	<i>Joy</i>	<i>Sadness</i>	<i>Disgust</i>	<i>Anger</i>	
Unpleasant surprise	Joyful	Disappointment	Disgust	Irritation	
Alarmed	Amusement			Indignation	
Amazement				Dissatisfaction	
Astonishment					
Pleasant surprise					
<i>non-basic emotion derivates</i>					
<i>Contempt</i>	<i>Desire</i>	<i>Stimulation</i>	<i>Boredom</i>	<i>Admiration</i>	<i>Satisfaction</i>
Contempt	Desire	Fascination	Boredom	Admiration	Satisfaction
	Avaricious	Curiosity			
	Yearn	Stimulation			
	Softened	Inspiration			
	Eagerness				

Table 1, Basic and subordinate-level product emotion types

Surprise is represented in pleasant, neutral, and unpleasant derivates: pleasant surprise (pleasant); amazement and astonishment (neutral); and frightened and alarmed (unpleasant). Sadness is represented by disappointment, and anger is represented by irritation, indignation, and dissatisfaction. Note that the basic emotion fear is not represented. This can be explained with the eliciting conditions for this emotion. Fear is experienced when we appraise a stimulus as a physical danger (Lazarus, 1991). It might not be relevant because nowadays products are believed to be too safe to be experienced as a real physical threat.

In addition to the emotions that are derivates of the basic emotions, the set of product relevant emotions also includes some emotions that cannot be derived from the basic emotions. The relations between, for instance, boredom, inspiration, desire, and admiration and the basic emotions are improbable. The last six columns of Table 1 show the emotions that are not subordinate derivates of the basic emotion types. The typology of product emotion types

should not only include the five conventional emotion types surprise, joy, sadness, disgust, and anger, but also the emotion types contempt, desire, stimulation, boredom, admiration, and satisfaction. The typology with all 13 emotion types is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1, Typology of basic product emotions

Note that the emotions in Table 1 apply to product appearance, and not to either owning or using a product. In an additional study Witsenburg and de Boer (2003) examined to what extent the emotions that are experienced in response to owning or using a product differ from those found in the study that focussed on appearance. It was found that all emotion types that are shown in Figure 1 (except for desire) can also be experienced in response to owning or using a product. They also found two additional emotion types, that is, security (e.g. relaxed, trusty), and insecurity (e.g. insecure and embarrassed). In Figure 1 these two additional emotion types are included between brackets. Each of the emotion types represents a category of emotions that people often experience in response to seeing, owning, or using a product. Examples of emotional responses to products that represent these types are given Table 2.

Surprise	“I am pleasantly surprised that this banal brand has marketed such an exciting car model.”
Desire	“I desire for this kangaroo ball because I anticipate it to be fun to play with.”
Disgust	“I am disgusted by this lamp’s indigestible kitsch design.”
Fascination	“I am fascinated by the interesting combination of soft and hard plastic in this toothbrush.”
Boredom	“I am bored by this disk container because it has dull colours, shapes, and materials.”
Joy	“I am amused by the funny combination of a coffee cup and a clock in a coffee-clock.”
Sadness	“I am disappointed by the inauthentic design of this retro-scooter.
Admiration	I admire the superior design of these ultra light glasses.”
Contempt	“I feel contemptuous towards this inferior polluting singing Christmas tree.”
Satisfaction	“I am satisfied because this telephone is exactly what a telephone should be: solid and simple.”
Anger	“I am dissatisfied because this lemon squeezer is too difficult to clean.
Security	“I feel confident about this dishwasher because I know it is of high quality.”
Insecurity	“I feel embarrassed by this video recorder because I have no idea how to operate it.”

Table 2, Examples of experienced emotions

These examples were drawn from a study in which 33 people were asked to photograph products that evoked emotions (that they personally experienced), and to write down why they had experienced these emotions (see Desmet, 2002). The results of this study supported the idea that although emotional responses are subjective, and that what disgusts one person,

might fascinate another, the conditions that give rise to these emotions are less subjective. Each emotion type should therefore be seen as representing a particular kind of eliciting conditions. Disgust type emotions, for example, are always evoked by ‘taking in or being too close to an indigestible object or idea,’ and contempt is always evoked by ‘an experienced inferiority’ (Lazarus, 1991).

Discussion

In this paper the expression ‘product emotions’ is used to indicate the emotions we experience in response to seeing, owning, or using a product. Note that these do not represent a ‘special type’ of emotions, and have the same qualities as the emotions we experience towards people and events (Desmet, 2002). The desire we feel to own a beautifully designed watch, and the indignation we feel about an expensive mobile telephone’s impractical tiny buttons, are not different from the desire and indignation we may experience towards people or social events. In the introduction, art was used to illustrate how seemingly simple artefacts can evoke complex and layered emotional responses. The question of whether or not product emotions are real emotions is similar to the question that underlies discussions in the field of ‘aesthetic emotions’ (i.e. emotions elicited by works of art; see Frijda and Schram, 1995). Most researchers who study aesthetic emotions consider emotional responses to art to be as genuine as emotions experienced in our daily lives. Lazarus (1991), for instance, concluded in his cognitive theory of emotions, that aesthetic emotions do not require special concepts, and that they can be explained with the same appraisal principles as ‘real’ emotions.

Nevertheless, it is interesting to observe that not less than six out of the 13 product emotion types are not derivatives of the basic emotion types, which, in psychology, are accepted as the core of our emotional repertoire. The reason may be that basic emotions are generally seen as products of our evolution and therefore universal, that is, found in all cultures, in very young children, and even in some animals (see Ekman 1984). These universal emotions are typically those that require a minimal cognitive processing (in situations when very rapid action is required). Ortony and his colleagues developed a structure of the affective lexicon in which they classified emotion words on the basis of their referential focus in affect-focal emotions, behavioural-focus emotions, and cognitive-focal emotions (Ortony *et al.* 1987). With ‘focus,’ they indicated the aspect of the emotion the word in question refers to. It appears that stimulation, boredom, contempt, and admiration all fall in the category of cognitive-focal

emotion words. Typically, what these emotions have in common is that they require more cognitive processing than basic emotions (Ortony *et al.* 1988). For instance, whereas fear requires a simple appraisal of physical threat, inspiration requires the more complex or sophisticated appraisal of mental illumination. Apparently, products often elicit emotions that are preceded by relatively complex (or evolved) appraisal. Note that (as opposed to the basic emotions) these ‘evolved’ emotions are typically restricted to human experiences (Lazarus, 1991).

Conclusion

The main reason for developing a typology of product relevant emotions, rather than using existing emotions sets, was twofold: (1) the basic emotion sets over-represent unpleasant emotions, and (2) these sets do not cover all emotions that seem to be relevant to products, such as boredom and inspiration. The product emotion typology overcomes both shortcomings: the number of pleasant and unpleasant emotions is balanced, and the set includes emotions that are more subtle than the basic or prototypical ones (e.g. admiration and satisfaction). Note that the 15 proposed product emotion types are not claimed to represent all emotional responses we may possibly experience in response to seeing, owning, or using a product. It is not too difficult to imagine how, for example, the emotion fear, which is not represented by these types, can be evoked by dangerous products such as chainsaws. Nevertheless, in our daily life experiencing fear in response to a conventional consumer product will be a scarce event. Thus, what these types do represent, are those emotions that we experience regularly in response to the products that surround us in our daily environment.

Understanding (and measuring) how different types of emotion are evoked by products (or product design) is relevant because it will facilitate designers in their attempts to ‘design for emotion.’ In addition, a typology can be used to develop tools that can be used to evaluate the emotional impact of products, to develop emotional design strategies, to define emotional target groups, or to investigate the emotional consistency of a company’s product portfolio. Ultimately, this kind of research will require the use of a theoretical and empirically validated set of emotion types. Although the proposed typology was developed on the basis of empirical research, additional research is required to establish its validity. Nonetheless, it does provide a set of emotion types that can be helpful in research endeavours towards understanding the nature of emotional responses evoked by products.

REFERENCES

- Aaker, D.A., Stayman, D.M., and R. Vezina. 1988. "Identifying feelings elicited by advertising." *Psychology and Marketing*, 5(1): 1-16.
- Batra, R., and M.B. Holbrook. 1990. "Developing a typology of affective responses to advertising." *Psychology and Marketing*, 7(1): 11-25.
- Davitz, J.R. 1969. *The language of emotions*. New York: Academic Press.
- Desmet, P.M.A. 2002. *Designing Emotions*. Unpublished doctoral thesis. Available from URL: <[http://studiolab.io.tudelft.nl/desmet/stories/storyReader\\$29](http://studiolab.io.tudelft.nl/desmet/stories/storyReader$29)>. [Accessed 2004 May 26].
- Desmet, P.M.A. 2003. "Measuring emotion: development and application of an instrument to measure emotional responses to products." In *Funology: From Usability to Enjoyment*. Edited by M.A. Blythe, A.F. Monk, K. Overbeeke, and P.C. Wright.
- Desmet, P.M.A., and E. Dijkhuis. 2003. "A wheelchair can be fun: a case of emotion-driven design." Proceedings of DPPI03, Pittsburg, USA.
- Ekman, P. 1971. "Universals and cultural differences in facial expressions of emotions." In *Nebraska Symposium on Motivation 1971*, edited by J.K. Cole, 207-283. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press.
- Ekman, P. 1984. "Expression and the nature of emotion." In *Approaches to Emotion*, edited by K.R. Scherer and P. Ekman, 319-244. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Frijda, N.H. 1986. *The emotions*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- Frijda, N.H., and D. Schram, eds. 1995. "Special issue on emotions and cultural products." *Poetics*, 23.
- Lazarus, R.S. 1991. *Emotion and Adaptation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Ortony, A. Clore, G.L., and A. Collins. 1988. *The cognitive structure of emotions*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ortony, A. Clore, G.L., and M.A. Foss. 1987. "The referential structure of the affective lexicon." *Cognitive Science*, 11: 341-364.
- Russell, J.A. 1980. "A circumplex model of affect." *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 39: 1161-1178.
- Shaver, P., Schwartz, J., Kirson, D., and C. O'Conner. 1987. "Emotion knowledge: further exploration of a prototype approach." *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 52(6): 1061-1086.
- Witsenburg, J., and F. de Boer. 2003. Een typologie van gebruiksemoties (in Dutch; a typology of usage emotions). Unpublished internal report. Delft: Delft University of Technology.

Dr. Pieter Desmet is assistant professor at the School of Industrial Design (Delft University of Technology). His main research interest is the relationship between product appearance and the emotional responses evoked by products. Currently he is a consulting researcher for companies in the fast moving consumer goods industry, the automotive industry, and to market research agencies. He is board member of the Design & Emotion Society, which is an international platform for researchers, designers, marketers, and the industry for the exchange of activities, developments, and insights in the field of design and emotion. Besides his research initiatives, he organized (design) workshops in Delft (The Netherlands), Potsdam (Germany), Tokyo (Japan), and Porto (Portugal).